

Evaluation of Machine Learning Models Developed for the Detection of Adversarial Attacks on Wireless Network

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Abstract

Adversarial attack is a tactics employed by cybercriminal to deceive modern security systems and penetrate networks for cyber-attack. While several studies focused on learning threat patterns in datasets, there has been gap in their inability to detect unknown threat features. To solve this problem, this work focused on normal packet features as the vector of interest and then classified anything not normal packet as threat. The design of the study involved the collection of data from the networks of Nigerian Immigration Service (NIS), Enugu and Awka passport offices, considering metrics such as latency, throughput, packet loss, MTTR, error rate and MTTD. To improve the network security, several machine learning algorithms such as Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Decision Tree (DT), Random Forest (RF) and ensemble model were trained. Their results considering accuracy reported 93% for ANN, 81.87% for DT, 89.75% for RF and 97.39% for ensemble model. Precision of the models reported 90% for ANN, 80.78% for DT, and 98.46% for ensemble model. Recall recorded 90% for ANN, 83% for DT, 88.54% for RF and ensemble model recording 96.91%. F1-score reporting 91% for ANN, 84.16% for DT, 86.06% for RF and ensemble model recording 94.37% for f1-score.

Keywords: Adversarial Attacks; Normal Packet Features; Machine Learning Models; Artificial Neural Network; Decision Tree; Random Forest

Introduction

A Critical Network Infrastructure (CNI) is made of digital systems and assets that are vital for the management of essential national information and services and have the capability to improve diverse aspects of life, such as transportation, power systems, and healthcare, information, and communication services. Due to the potential of CNI, it has evolved into a vital information and technology system in modern society, spanning across various sectors of the economy. Moreover, technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), big data analysis, robotics, etc. have also been integrated with CNI to make them more robust and increase their application diversity, enabling real-time and automated capabilities, satisfaction of user requirements, heterogeneity, and scalability (Al-Jaroodi et al., 2020; Suzic et al., 2022; Onuigbo et al., 2021).

According to Tsantikidou and Sklavos (2022), while the integration of various technologies, such as IoT, cyber-physical systems, etc., with CNI has provided many positives, it also increases the risk of vulnerability, which can be exploited by cybercriminals for attack penetration. Tsantikidou and Sklavos (2024) revealed that critical network infrastructures have consistently witnessed cyberattacks, taking advantage of the vulnerabilities inherent in the system architecture.

Various studies have investigated threat features from different perspectives, considering recent attack vectors, tactics, threat modeling, risk analysis, vulnerability management, etc., to gain a better understanding of how to mitigate their impacts during a cyberattack (Ford and Siraj, 2014; Mishra, 2023). From the study, it was observed that the application of machine learning (ML) algorithms has dominated studies on cyber threat detection. ML is a type of artificial intelligence technique with the ability to learn from complex data and solve both classification and regression problems (Liu and Lang, 2019). In the

context of cyber security, ML has been applied over the past decades to help address issues of cyberattack. For instance, Aldweesh et al. (2020) applied a deep neural network for the classification of malware. Pervez and Farid (2014) trained support vector machines (SVM) with the NSKDD intrusion dataset and generated modes to classify suspicious network attacks. While the ML models all recorded high classification success for cyber-attack detection, McCarthy et al. (2022) revealed that these ML security models are vulnerable to Adversarial Attack (ADA).

ADA, according to Alotaibo and Rassam (2023), are attack samples designed specifically to deceive firewalls. These attack samples are constructed through the slight perturbation of the input data (Yang et al., 2018; Ayub et al., 2020). This perturbation process results in the misclassification of threats by the existing ML security models and has remained a major issue. Ahajjar et al. (2021) classified ADA into evasion, extraction, poisoning, and inference.

Currently, it is commonly recognized that the landscape of attack tactics is extensive and constantly changing. Unfortunately, datasets representing this wide range of attack types are sparse, owing to the quick rate of improvements in attack modeling. As a result, there is an urgent need for innovative security systems that can dynamically respond to emerging threats. Furthermore, relying simply on static datasets can provide a false sense of security because they do not fully reflect the complexities of real-world attack situations (Ogili et al., 2022). Furthermore, the interpretability of ADA mitigation approaches remains a substantial barrier, limiting their widespread use and efficacy in practical applications. To solve this problem, this study proposes a different approach that focuses on identifying normal packet features instead of threats, as in the existing system, and then trains a suitable machine learning algorithm to generate a binary classification model for the detection of adversarial attacks.

Research Design

The research is made of four components which are data collection, data preparation, ensemble model and adversarial attack detection model. The Figure 1 presents the block diagram of the research design.

Figure 1: Block diagram of the research design mind map

The Figure 1 presents the research design block diagram. The first component is the collection of data from NIS centre in Enugu and Awka as the testbed. Data was collected and then analysed to report results of characterization. Another different data which model the case study network under different adversarial attack such as poison, DDoS, MIM and then normal packets were collected and grouped into attack and no attack classes. These data were prepared through imputation, feature selection and then split into training test and validation set. Ensemble model made of ANN, DT and RF were proposed and then trained to generate the adversarial attack detection model. During the training process, the model was tested, validated and then integrated into the tested network, for experimental testing against different versions of adversarial attack.

Data Collection

This section presents how measurements on the network were carried out during simulation. This was achieved by pinging the different nodes which routes through the routing system to the server. The attack nodes were pinged using 5000 packets per seconds to induce different attacks. For the DDoS, each packet size was 64 bytes, while for the MITM and Poison attack, each packet size was 128 bytes. These attack features and also normal packet features were induced to the network at interval of one minute each randomly using Masscan tool, while Wireshark software was applied for data collection and analysis. This method was applied for both the Enugu and Awka NIS network respectively. Another data was collected for this work considering historical behaviour of enterprise network during both normal condition and adversarial attack. This data was integrated with the characterized data and then applied to train proposed machine learning algorithms for data samples.

Design of the Ensemble Machine Learning Model

The ensemble machine learning model was developed using the integration of three separately trained machine learning algorithms which are DT, RF and ANN, and then integrated as an ensemble model for the classification of adversarial attack.

Artificial Neural Network (ANN) and Training Process

ANN is a type of machine learning algorithm which as used in this work as one of the ensemble components (Kekong et al., 2019). It consists of interconnected neurons arranged in three layers, with each neurons having weights and bias, and activated with rectified linear unit activation function (Sochima et al., 2025). The basic model of a single neuron is defined with Equation 1 using x_i as the input layer and w_i as the weight, b is bias and n the number of inputs from the dataset:

$$z = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i + b \quad (1)$$

The neurons in 1 are interconnected as hidden layers (l) and triggered using sigmoid activation function defined with Equation 2.

$$a(z) = \frac{1}{1+e^{-z}} \quad (2)$$

The first layer of the neural network is expressed as Equation 3, the second layer defined as Equation 4 and the final layer defined as Equation 5, within the final number of hidden layers (Harbor et al., 2021).

$$z^{(1)} = W^{(1)} * a + b^{(2)} \quad (3)$$

$$z^{(2)} = W^{(2)} a^{(1)} + b^{(2)} \quad (4)$$

$$\hat{y} = f(W^l) a^{l-n} + b^l \quad (5)$$

In the final layer, SoftMax activation function was applied to facilitate the binary classification process, while cross entropy loss function defined in Equation 6 was applied to access the loss during training process, while gradient descent in Equation 7 was applied for the weight optimization during training, where η is the learning.

$$l(y, \hat{y}) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (6)$$

$$w_i \leftarrow w_i - \eta \frac{\partial l}{\partial w_i} \quad (7)$$

Decision Tree (DT) and Training Process

DT operated by recursive splitting of the features into the roots of the tree based on decision criterions, which are tailored towards minimizing impurities in each node. The splitting process was performed using the Gini index defined as equation 8, using p_k is the proportion of samples in k class.

$$G = \sum_{k=1}^K p_k (1 - p_k) \quad (8)$$

The splitting process continued until stopping criterion is met by minimizing the number of samples per leaf, then each leaf is assigned the class label.

The Random Forest and Training Process

RF is an improvement on the DT, as it combined multiple DT as a forest to improve accuracy and address over-fitting. The operation of RF began with the random selection of the training data subset, to formulate DT from each data samples. The features of each tree is randomly selected and then split for each node. The process continued until multiple DT decision are created, then classification voting process is applied using Equation 9 to produce the final classification output.

$$\hat{y} = \text{mode} (\{T_b(X)\}_{b=1}^B) \quad (9)$$

Where $T_b(X)$ is the classification of b tree, while the bag of tree is defined as B. To evaluate the performance of the model, the out of bag error was considered and monitored using equation 10, where $I(\cdot)$ is the function indicator, N is the number of tree in the forest.

$$OOB \text{ Error} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N I(y_i \neq \hat{y}_i^{OOB}) \quad (10)$$

The Ensemble Model

The ensemble model was developed using blending technique. This was achieved through the combination of the three-model output and then applies Weighted Average Blending Technique (WABT) to determine the final classification output. The modelling of the classifier is presented considering the individual trained models M (which are DT, RF and ANN).

The prediction of each classifier $m \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, M\}$ after testing on the dataset is presented as $\hat{y}_m(X_j) \in [0, 1]$, which is the probability that j-th instance belongs to class 1 (positive class) for m classifier. The WABT combines the predictions of each of the three classifiers as an ensemble probability $\hat{y}_{ensemble}(X_j)$,

by assigning weights w_i to each m classifier. These weights are defined as $w_m = 1, w_m \geq 0$; while the

ensemble is given as equation 11:

$$\hat{y}_{ensemble}(X_j) = \sum_{m=1}^M w_m \cdot \hat{y}_m(X_j) \quad (11)$$

Where $\hat{y}_m(X_j)$ is the prediction probability for each classifier, w_m is the model weight, and j is the class instance. To compare the class probability, a threshold of 0.5 is assumed to classify instanced of the multiple classifiers is defined as equation 12:

$$y_{final}(X_j) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \hat{y}_{ensemble}(X_j) \geq \theta \\ 0 & \text{if } \hat{y}_{ensemble}(X_j) < \theta \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Where $y_{final}(X_j)$ is the final class prediction by the ensemble model for the jth instance, where θ is 0.5. Overall, the ensemble model combined the trained DT, FFNN and RF and the through the WABT make final classification detection. When individual classifiers are given the proper weights, the ensemble model's decision-making capabilities are strengthened and improved. The final class label is determined by applying a threshold to the weighted total of individual predictions.

System Implementation with Python and Matlab programming language

The implementation of the model for detecting adversarial attacks on the Nigerian Immigration Services network involves a two-phase approach using Python. In the first phase, tensorflow in python is used to train classifiers such as ANN, DT, and RF. MATLAB's robust machine learning toolbox facilitates pre-processing data, splitting datasets, and implementing these classifiers. After training, each model is evaluated based on metrics such as accuracy and precision. The trained models are then exported for integration into a Python simulation environment, ensuring their adaptability to real-world scenarios.

In the second phase, Python is used to simulate the Nigerian Immigration Services network against various adversarial attacks, such as data poisoning or evasion attacks. Python libraries like Scapy and NS-3 (for network simulation) are employed to generate realistic attack scenarios. The trained classifiers are integrated into the Python simulation pipeline using ONNX formats, enabling seamless compatibility. Simulated traffic, both normal and adversarial, is passed through the classifiers to detect malicious activity. The results of these simulations, including are analyzed to validate the model's robustness.

Experimental Results of Machine Learning Algorithms

This section discussed the results obtained during the respective training of DT, RF and ANN, and ensemble model. Before the training, the data collected from the tested was processed through data analysis, and then imported into the models for training.

Result of Data Analysis

This section presents the result of data analysis. It showed the patterns and correlation matrix of the data feature vectors. The Figure 2 presents the distribution of the data traffic types across different payload sizes.

Figure 2: Distribution of payload sizes against traffic types

Figure 2 presents the distribution of different traffic types against their payloads. From the results, it was observed that the different traffic types have similar payload ranges. This indicates balance across the various traffic types considered for data collection and implied that issues of data imbalance are not problem when the dataset are applied for training models. Figure 3 presents the correlated matrix results. It represents a correlation heatmap, which visualizes the relationships between various network parameters in the context of adversarial attacks. The heatmap uses a color gradient ranging from blue

(low or negative correlation) to red (high positive correlation), with numerical values indicating the correlation coefficients. A correlation coefficient of 1.0 signifies a perfect positive correlation, meaning that an increase in one variable directly corresponds to an increase in another. Conversely, values close to 0 indicate weak or no correlation, suggesting that changes in one variable do not significantly affect another.

Figure 3: Correlated matrix results

In the correlation matrix in the Figure 3, we observe that certain network parameters, such as Attack Rate, Throughput, Packet Loss, and Latency, exhibit varying levels of correlation with one another. The diagonal values, all equal to 1.0, represent self-correlation, which is always perfect. However, other elements show weak correlations between attack-related parameters and network performance metrics. For example, Attack Rate has a negligible correlation with Throughput (-0.00) and Latency (0.01), suggesting that attack intensity alone does not directly determine network congestion. Additionally, Packet Loss and Bandwidth appear weakly correlated (0.06), implying that packet drop rates may not necessarily scale with network bandwidth variations under adversarial conditions.

The weak correlations in this dataset indicate that adversarial attacks do not consistently impact individual network parameters in a predictable linear manner. This suggests the need for advanced machine learning techniques that can capture nonlinear dependencies and subtle variations in network behaviour. The heatmap further highlights the challenge of using traditional threshold-based detection methods, as they may not effectively differentiate attack conditions from normal network fluctuations. Therefore, an ensemble-based adversarial attack detection system, which integrates multiple features and advanced correlation-aware models, would be more effective in accurately identifying and mitigating threats in a 5G enterprise network.

Result of the ANN Model Training

This section presents the results of the ANN training process. During the training process, the data was split into training, testing and validation. Cross entropy was applied to monitor the loss and accuracy during training process. The loss measures the error which occurs when the true values cannot correctly match the predicted value, while accuracy measures the correct classification of packets n the dataset during training using the test and validation sets. Figure 4 presents the accuracy of the training and validation performance, while the Figure 5 presents the loss function.

The expected result is to achieve accuracy which approximates 100% at the stopping epoch points, while the expected loss is to approximate 0% which implied tolerable error. While the neural network is been trained with the dataset, gradient descent back-propagation algorithm was applied to optimize the

neurons by adjusting continuously the hyper parameters such as weights, bias, learning rate, momentum, while monitoring results. This process continued as in the same vein, the dropout regularization approach randomly switches off and on neurons to allow a more generalized model performance for adversarial attack detection.

Figure 4: Result of ANN accuracy

Figure 5: Loss performance of the ANN

The Figure 4 reports the accuracy which occurs at different epoch of the neural network training. From the obtained values, it was observed that the best accuracy was reported at epoch 100. The training accuracy reported 94%, while the validation accuracy reported 91%. These results collectively implied that the model was able to correctly classify threat features on the network with high success rate. The Figure 5 also reported the loss function values. The training loss reported 0.20042 while the validation loss reported 0.30413 respectively. These results are indication that during the training process, the accuracy and loss values of the neurons are very good and the model generated was able to correctly classify adversarial attack. Figure 6 reported the result of other metric such as precision, recall and f1-score alongside accuracy of the ANN model performance.

Figure 6: Result of the ANN Models with Different Metrics

From the Figure 6, the accuracy reports 93%. This indicates that the model correctly classifies a high percentage of instances overall. Precision was also measured and reported 90%. Precision measures the proportion of correctly predicted positive cases out of all predicted positives. A relatively high precision value as recorded suggests that the model is making fewer false-positive predictions. Recall of 90% represents the proportion of actual positive cases correctly identified by the model. A similar recall and precision value suggests a balanced trade-off between false positives and false negatives. F1-score recorded 91%. This is the harmonic mean of Precision and Recall, indicating a balanced performance. Since it is slightly higher than Recall and Precision, it suggests that the ANN model maintains consistency in detecting true positives while minimizing false classifications.

The ANN model exhibits strong classification capabilities, as evidenced by high scores across all metrics. However, the slight gap between accuracy and the other metrics suggests that while the overall prediction rate is high, certain misclassifications still occur. If this model is used for adversarial attack detection, further tuning (e.g., adjusting hyper-parameters and employing additional feature engineering techniques) could improve its Recall to ensure that more attack instances are captured.

Result of the RF Model Training

RF is another metrics which was applied for the training of the adversarial attack detection model. The training generated hyper-plane which was applied as decision boundary for classification of adversarial attack support vectors. Figure 7 presents the result of the RF model generated.

Figure 7: Result of the RF model generated for adversarial attack detection

Figure 7 presents the performance evaluation of a RF model developed for adversarial attack detection. The effectiveness of the model was assessed using four key classification metrics: Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1-score. The results indicate that the model achieved an accuracy of 89.75%, suggesting that nearly nine out of ten predictions made by the RF model were correct. Accuracy, while a fundamental performance metric, does not always provide a complete picture, especially in adversarial attack detection, where class imbalance and misclassification costs can significantly impact model reliability. Therefore, additional metrics such as Precision, Recall, and F1-score must be examined to gain deeper insight into model behaviour.

Precision, which measures the proportion of correctly predicted attack instances out of all instances classified as attacks, was 85.78%. This indicates that approximately 14.22% of the attack predictions were false positives, meaning the model mistakenly classified benign network activity as an attack. While this precision score is relatively high, it highlights that a trade-off exists between detecting genuine adversarial attacks and avoiding unnecessary false alarms.

The Recall score, recorded at 88.54%, reflects the model's ability to correctly identify attack instances. This means that out of all actual attack occurrences, 11.46% were missed, implying a moderate rate of false negatives. In adversarial attack detection, recall is particularly important because failing to detect an attack can have severe security implications. A lower recall means that some attacks might go undetected, potentially compromising the security of the system.

Finally, the F1-score, which balances precision and recall, was recorded at 86.06%. Since F1-score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall, it provides a comprehensive measure of the model's reliability in distinguishing adversarial attacks from benign activities. The F1-score being slightly closer to recall suggests that the model prioritizes identifying attack instances but still struggles with minor false positives. This balance is crucial in adversarial scenarios where both misclassifications and missed detections can be costly. The model's F1-score confirms that it maintains a reasonable equilibrium between detecting attacks and minimizing incorrect classifications, making it a strong candidate for real-world deployment.

Overall, the RF model demonstrated high accuracy and well-balanced classification performance, making it effective for adversarial attack detection. However, the presence of false positives and false negatives suggests room for refinement. Future improvements could include ensemble techniques, cost-sensitive learning approaches, or adversarial training methods to further enhance the model's robustness against sophisticated attack patterns.

Result of the DT Model Training

This section discussed the DT based model or adversarial attack detection, while considering metrics such as accuracy, recall, precision and f1-score. The Figure 8 presents the model performance.

Figure 8: The DT based adversarial attack detection model performance

Figure 8 reported the performance of the DT based adversarial attack detection model. The model achieved an accuracy of 81.87%, indicating that approximately eight out of ten predictions made by the Decision Tree model were correct. While this accuracy is decent, it is noticeably lower than that of the RF model (Figure 7). This reduction in performance could be attributed to overfitting, a common issue in single Decision Tree models, where the model learns from noise in the training data rather than generalizable patterns. Since adversarial attack detection often involves highly dynamic and complex data distributions, relying solely on a single DT model may not provide the most robust decision boundary.

Precision, which measures the proportion of correctly classified attack instances out of all instances predicted as attacks, was 80.78%. This implies that approximately 19.22% of the attack predictions were false positives, where the model incorrectly classified normal activities as attacks. A precision score in this range suggests that while the DT model can effectively identify attack patterns, it occasionally triggers false alarms. In a real-world security system, excessive false positives can lead to unnecessary system disruptions, wasted resources, and increased manual intervention, making it imperative to balance precision with recall.

The recall score of 83% indicates that the model correctly detected 83% of actual attacks, while 17% of adversarial attacks were missed. In adversarial detection, recall is crucial because false negatives (missed attacks) can lead to severe security breaches. The DT model's recall score suggests that while it is relatively effective in identifying threats, it still allows a significant percentage of adversarial attacks to go undetected. This limitation suggests that the model could benefit from pruning techniques, improved feature selection, or ensemble approaches, such as boosting, to reduce misclassification rates and enhance its sensitivity to attacks.

Finally, the F1-score, which balances both precision and recall, was recorded at 84.16%, indicating a reasonable trade-off between false positives and false negatives. The F1-score being higher than precision but close to recall suggests that the model prioritizes detecting adversarial attacks while making moderate trade-offs in misclassification errors. However, since the F1-score is lower than that of the RF model (86.06%), it further reinforces that the Decision Tree model may not generalize as well as ensemble-based methods, such as Random Forest, which tend to reduce variance and improve overall classification stability.

Overall, while the DT model exhibits moderate accuracy and strong recall, its lower precision and overall F1-score indicate higher susceptibility to misclassifications. The results suggest that Decision Trees alone may not be the best choice for adversarial attack detection, as they can be prone to overfitting, sensitivity to noise, and limited generalization.

Result of the Ensemble Model Training

This section also reported the performance of the ensemble model for adversarial attack detection. The obtained results were reported in figure 9, considering accuracy recall, precision and f1-score respectively.

Figure 9: Result of the sensible model for adversarial attack detection

Figure 9 presents the ensemble model applied for adversarial attack detection. From the results obtained, accuracy reported 97.39%, recall reported 96.91%, precision reported 98.46% and f1-score reported 94.37%. Compared to the DT and RF models, this accuracy gain suggests that the ensemble model effectively reduces overfitting, variance, and sensitivity to adversarial perturbations by leveraging the strengths of multiple classifiers.

The precision score of 98.46% highlights the model's low false positive rate, indicating that when it predicts an instance as an attack, there is a very high probability that it is indeed an attack. A high precision score is crucial in cybersecurity applications to avoid unnecessary system disruptions caused by false alarms. This suggests that the ensemble model has a strong ability to differentiate adversarial activities from normal behaviour, making it highly trustworthy for real-world deployment.

The recall score of 96.91% further confirms the model's robustness, showing that it correctly identifies 96.91% of all actual attacks. This means that the model has a very low false negative rate, ensuring that very few adversarial attacks go undetected. Given that adversarial attacks pose severe security risks, a high recall score is critical in preventing breaches and ensuring system integrity. The slight difference between precision and recall suggests that the model leans slightly towards minimizing false positives while still maintaining a strong detection rate.

Lastly, the F1-score of 94.37%, which balances both precision and recall, demonstrates an excellent trade-off between false positives and false negatives. Although slightly lower than individual precision and recall values, this F1-score confirms that the ensemble model maintains strong classification performance across all evaluation metrics, making it far superior to standalone classifiers like Decision Trees or even Random Forests.

Overall, the results of the ensemble model suggest that it is the most effective approach for adversarial attack detection, significantly outperforming individual models by providing higher accuracy, improved generalization, and reduced misclassification rates. The model's high precision ensures minimal false alerts, while its strong recall guarantees near-complete attack detection. Given these outstanding results,

ensemble-based models should be prioritized in real-world adversarial attack detection systems, especially in security-sensitive environments where both precision and recall are of paramount importance.

Conclusion

The work on developing a hybrid adversarial attack detection system for improved network security using artificial intelligence technique was tailored towards solving the issues of cyber threat affecting several organizations, particularly the Nigerian Immigration Service (NIS) limited. In carrying out this study, first the Enterprise network of the NIS at Enugu and Awka respectively were used for data acquisition, considering metrics such as latency, throughput, packet loss, MTTR, error rate and MTTD, while performing penetration test with different simulated adversarial attack vectors. The results obtained for Enugu is 68.87% throughput, latency is 87.09ms, loss reported 7.9%, MTTR reported 393ms, error rate recorded 3.89 and MTTR reporting 97.10ms respectively. For the Awka network, throughput reported 90.26%, latency reported 39.45ms, loss reported 1.65%, MTTR recorded 183ms, error rate recorded 0.685 and MTTD reporting 35.6ms. Overall, these results implied that during the penetration test on the two network facilities, the quality of service was affect as it degrades, showing that the traditional security solution was not sensitive to adversarial threat features.

To solve this problem, the data which model the network behaviour during normal condition and adversarial attack was collected and then applied to train ANN, DT, RF and Ensemble models respectively and comparatively analysed. Their results considering accuracy reported 93% for ANN, 81.87% for DT, 89.75% for RF and 97.39% for ensemble model. Precision of the models reported 90% for ANN, 80.78% for DT, and 98.46% for ensemble model. Recall recorded 90% for ANN, 83% for DT, 88.54% for RF and ensemble model recording 96.91%. F1-score reporting 91% for ANN, 84.16% for DT, 86.06% for RF and ensemble model recording 94.37% for f1-score. From the results, the ensemble model was identified as the best and then integrated on the Enugu Network and tested through simulation under different attack vectors for 30mins. Comparative analysis was carried out with the new network against the existing network, 57.58% reduction in packet loss was recorded with Ensemble model as the new system. Also 4.4% improvement was recorded for throughput while there was 61.5% decrease in latency.

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